

Has Buy Now Pay Later become a symbol of hedonistic lifestyle among young people?

Yulisty Diar Rochma¹, Retno Tanding Suryandari²

¹Master of Management Study Program, Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Sebelas Maret, Indonesia

²Tenure Lecturer, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The advancement of technology and the internet has driven significant transformations in the global business landscape and consumer lifestyles. One notable innovation in financial technology (Fintech) is Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL), a digital financial service that enables consumers to make purchases without immediate payment, thereby creating a more appealing and instant shopping experience. This service has gained substantial popularity among younger generations, particularly Generation Z, who account for 56.7% of Pay Later users. This study aims to analyze the influence of BNPL on hedonistic lifestyle, facility utilization, and impulsive buying behavior using a quantitative approach involving questionnaire distribution and analysis through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings reveal a positive relationship between BNPL usage and both facility utilization and hedonistic lifestyle, which ultimately contributes to increased impulsive buying behavior among young consumers in Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: buy now pay later, gen Z, hedonistic, impulsive buying, financial technology, lifestyle

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of e-commerce, driven by tremendous advancements in the Internet and technology, has led to a new paradigm in business worldwide (Joines et al., 2003). Technology has become a significant aspect of human life that profoundly influences globalization in the millennial era. The lifestyle of society is changing rapidly due to the increasing use and development of information technology. Numerous enterprises specializing in technology-driven financial solutions, commonly referred to as Financial Technology (Fintech) companies, have emerged in response to the needs of the public. Financial technology is a collection of entities that combine technological features with the characteristics of financial services (Ginantra et al., 2020).

Currently, the most widely recognized platform in society is Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL). The BNPL phenomenon enchants consumers to make online purchases with the option of paying in installments, creating a more engaging shopping experience. In contrast, traditional bank loans necessitate a thorough assessment of the borrower's ability to repay the loan. The key distinction lies in the social aspect, as banks bear the responsibility of lending money in accordance with the borrower's capacity, with stipulations for loan repayment. On the flip side, what often proves problematic is that BNPL platforms are not bound by social obligations and may escape scrutiny from traditional financial institutions that establish norms and regulations.

The Financial Services Authority (OJK) has recorded the growth of Buy Now Pay Later (BNPL) financing based on SLIK, for the portion of banking loans recorded at 0.25%, and continues to experience high growth every year. As of February 2025, BNPL's credit debit balance grew 36.60% yoy (January 2025: 46.45% yoy) to Rp21.98 trillion, with the number of accounts reaching 23.66 million (January 2025: 24.44 million). A very significant increase reached 25.85% in just two years, recorded by the Finance Company from the previous year 2023 was only around 33.25% year-on-year (YoY) and in February 2025 it increased to 59.1% yoy. In the same period the previous year, there were 54.70 million Buy Now Pay Later contracts. Supported by financial technology, which is a technology-based industry aimed at making financial systems and service delivery more effective and efficient (Ginantra et al., 2020), it is mentioned that financial technology provides various financial services and products in a convenient and advantageous manner for users.

Paylater is one of the payment methods that offers installment facilities without a credit card, allowing users to buy products now and pay for the transaction at a later date. In the past year, pay later has become a key strategy for various e-commerce platforms to attract users, with platforms such as Shopee, Traveloka, Tokopedia, Lazada, and Blibli incorporating it into their offerings (Eviana, & Saputra, 2022). Meanwhile, looking at one year later, precisely in March 2023, Kredivo, together with Katadata Insight Center

(KIC), conducted a survey to examine the trend of Paylater usage in Indonesia. The results showed that out of the 6,403 Paylater users surveyed, the majority, or 39.9% of them, used the service more than once a month.

The interest in Paylater is predominantly from consumers in the younger demographic. The use of digital financial products has become a daily habit among the younger generation. Specifically for installment payments, among the younger demographic, the use of the recently popular Paylater method surpasses the use of credit cards. Credit cards are utilized by 7.6% of millennials and Gen Z, whereas Paylater is used nearly twice as much (13.6%). When comparing the two generations, the use of Paylater is more significant among millennials, with 16.5% of millennials surveyed by KIC stating that they use Paylater. As for Gen Z respondents, only 9.7% have used Paylater products. The increasing popularity of Paylater, consumers often find it challenging to resist their shopping impulses towards enticing products (Widawati, 2011), The concept is known as Impulse Buying. Impulse Buying can be explained as spontaneous and unplanned purchasing behavior, where individuals make direct and instant purchases influenced by strong impulses and feelings of happiness (Rook, 1987).

In the context of the background issues outlined above, this research aims to delve deeper into the relationship between Paylater service users, hedonistic lifestyle, and the utilization of facilities in impulsive buying behavior. The study aspires to provide a comprehensive understanding and serve as a reference guide, offering benchmarks that can yield numerous benefits for both consumers and business owners integrating Paylater features into their operations. Furthermore, the research endeavors to offer insights into the specific patterns of behavior exhibited by the Indonesian community when utilizing Paylater. This information can contribute to discourse surrounding target market identification for businesses, thereby enhancing strategic decision-making. The anticipated outcomes of this study are expected to furnish valuable references for stakeholders, facilitating the incorporation of Paylater facilities into their business models.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Buy Now, Pay Later

Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) is a service available at the time of purchase, offering consumers the option to defer payment by dividing it into one or several interest-free installments. BNPL is predominantly used in online transactions, and its service providers are often separate entities from retailers (Guttman-Kenney et al., 2023). In the use of Pay later as a preferred e-commerce transaction payment method among millennials, there are several advantages (Aristanti, 2020). The process is quick and convenient, making 'Buy Now Pay Later' an easily accessible method, especially in urgent situations. Additionally, the varied tenors offer flexibility, allowing consumers to customize the payment period according to their preferences and financial capabilities. The Paylater tenor options across various e-commerce platforms and e-wallets range from 1 to 12 months. Opting for a shorter tenor typically entails lower interest rates. Furthermore, the increasing popularity of Paylater has sparked intense competition among companies, leading to enticing promotions and offers for users, ultimately encouraging higher consumer spending (Azzahra, 2022).

As users of the Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) feature, Generation Z is a demographic that heralds BNPL as a savior in promptly fulfilling their desires and needs without enduring prolonged waits. The advent of BNPL can be seen as a strategic choice touted as a customer magnet for e-commerce companies. It's no secret that there exists a close and symbiotic relationship between e-commerce companies and the Paylater feature. E-commerce platforms collaborating to offer products through BNPL not only capture consumer interest but also sweeten the deal with the allure of deferred payments (Pratika et al., 2021). BNPL essentially opens up opportunities for consumers to make purchases without an immediate financial outlay, making it more enticing and positioning it as an innovative strategy for e-commerce companies to attract and retain customers.

H1: BNPL positively influences Hedonistic Value

H2: BNPL positively influences the utilization of facilities.

Hedonistic Value

Consumer behavior aspects related to multisensory, fantasy, and emotional experiences when interacting with products have been explored by Hirschman and Holbrook (1982). The hedonistic nature born from shopping experiences often involves various sensory modalities, such as touch, taste, scent, and sound, enabling creative thinking and triggering emotional responses. Hedonistic consumption behavior can have indirect effects on well-being by enhancing consumer satisfaction beyond the dominion of practical needs. Hedonic consumption represents a shopping experience category that goes beyond fulfilling basic

human needs. It provides a rich sensory experience, stimulates the imagination, and creates a palette of positive emotions. On the flip side, hedonic shopping experiences can positively impact an individual's overall life satisfaction. It is believed to enhance satisfaction and happiness across various aspects of life (Zhong & Mitchell, 2010).

Several studies indicate that the instant convenience and satisfaction offered by BNPL can encourage a hedonistic lifestyle among consumers, where they prioritize momentary pleasure over long-term financial stability. A Hedonistic Lifestyle reflects a desire to immediately experience pleasure and enjoyment. BNPL does not permit impulsive behavior without any notice, which can lead to significant debt accumulation if not managed wisely.

H3. Hedonistic value positively influences Impulsive Buying

Utilizing Facilities

The environment or conditions that facilitate or support an individual in using or adopting a technology are referred to as Supportive Infrastructure. This encompasses the individual's belief that organizational infrastructure, such as policies, procedures, and management support, as well as technical infrastructure, such as the required hardware and software, is available and ready to be used to support the utilization of the technology (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000a). Facilities are also evident in the resources used, such as the internet, mobile memory, and hardware, as well as knowledge to enhance the intention to use technology, reflecting the conditions that support it (Gupta et al., 2017).

Technology that has services, resources, and user-friendly feature support can enhance motivation for its use. For example, with the emergence of one technological innovation that simplifies financial systems and creates a system for financial transactions, this innovation involves payment, settlement, and adjustment. Online transactions simplify financial management, especially when supported by regulations such as POJK regulating financial technology, as well as the availability of online credit services without a credit card with easy disbursement and refund processes (Lantini et al., 2023).

This inspires many individuals to opt for Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) services due to the convenience offered by e-commerce platforms. When engaging in online shopping, the ability to leverage BNPL provides significant flexibility for consumers. With BNPL, they can acquire products without an immediate payment obligation, often easing the burden of substantial expenses or uncertain financial situations. Moreover, BNPL offers consumers the opportunity to try and experience products before committing to full payment, adding significant value. The availability of BNPL services not only attracts customers to e-commerce platforms based on their product offerings but also by providing a flexible payment option that enhances convenience and buyer satisfaction. Consequently, many people are inclined to utilize BNPL services when shopping online.

H4. Utilizing facilities positively influences Impulsive Purchases

Impulsive Buying

In prior research, impulsive buying has been defined as unplanned purchases resulting from the comparison between alternative purchase intentions and actual outcomes. The focus of these studies is on the comparison between the actual shopping results and the preconceived shopping intentions (Kollat & Willett, 1967). More recent studies have conceptualized impulsive buying as a process and outcome mechanism within the psychological domain, occurring when a consumer experiences an unplanned, immediate urge to purchase something. This tendency is often ongoing and can be described as a complex, hedonic stimulus that may trigger emotional conflicts (Rook, 1987).

Consumers often engage in higher consumption, especially regarding fashion items, technology, and entertainment. The use of BNPL can be appealing to them as it allows for immediate fulfillment of consumption desires. However, excessive use of BNPL can lead to high debt and disrupt their financial stability. Impulsive buying is viewed as less advantageous consumption behavior because it often involves spending money without careful consideration, purchasing impractical or unnecessary items, and the potential financial or emotional risks associated with such purchases (Iyer et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study employs an explanatory design with the aim of elucidating the occurrence of an event and constructing or testing a theory. In terms of the temporal dimension, this research falls within the realm of a cross-sectional study, wherein data collection occurs within a single period. Quantitative data collection is executed by distributing questionnaires to consumers utilizing the Paylater, BNPL service. Primary data is obtained from respondents through the questionnaire, while secondary data is sourced

from statistical agencies, websites, and government data. The data collection method was self-administered using an electronic questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale.

The population for this study comprises users of the Paylater service on e-commerce platforms, with the sample size determined based on the minimum sufficiency expected in Partial Least Square-SEM (PLS-SEM) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) methods. The sampling technique employed is non-probabilistic with a purposive approach, where information is gathered from population members assuming they meet specific criteria.

RESULTS

Geographic Information

This study involves a total of 97 respondents, reflecting various characteristics as outlined in Table 1 below :

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

CATEGORIES	DESCRIPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER	Women	55	56.7%
	Men	42	43.3%
AGE RANGE	17 - 26 (Z Generation)	55	56.7%
	27 - 42 (Milennial Generation)	35	36.1%
	43 - 58 (X Generation)	7	7.2%
PAYLATER PROVIDERS	Spaylater	47	48.5%
	OVO Paylater	35	36.1%
	Gopay Paylater	12	12.4%
	Traveloka Paylater	3	3.1%
OCCUPATION	Civil Servant	5	5.2%
	Company Employee	22	22.7%
	Freelancer	8	8.2%
	Entrepreneur	13	13.4%
	Student	32	32.9%
	Housewife	11	11.3%
	Others	6	6.2%
AVERAGE MONTHLY EXPENDITURE AMOUNT	<Rp 500.000,00	6	6.2%
	Rp 501.000,00 - Rp 1.500.000,00	44	45.4%
	Rp 1.501.000,00 - Rp 3.000.000,00	40	41.2%
	>Rp 3.000.000	7	7.2%

Table 2. Constructs and measurement items

Construction	Codes	Origin	Items
Buy Now Pay Later	BNPL1	(Hilmi & Pratika, 2021)	1. The process of applying for the Paylater feature can be easily completed.
	BNPL2		2. The application for the Paylater feature is facilitated through a swift process.
	BNPL3		3. Paylater feature offers attractively low-interest rates.
Utilizing	MF1	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)	1. I have an <i>e-commerce</i> application to use the Paylater feature.
	MF2		2. I possess ample know-how to leverage the Paylater functionality within the realm of e-

Facilities			commerce.
	MF3		3. I believe the Paylater feature is compatible with other financial technologies I use.
	HV1		1. Shopping with Paylater is truly delightful.
Hedonic Value	HV2	(Babin & Attaway, 2000)	2. When using Paylater, I feel a continuous desire to shop, not out of necessity but because I genuinely want to
	HV3		3. Compared to other activities, the time spent shopping with Paylater feels more enjoyable.
	IB1		1. The Buy Now, Pay Later feature creates a strong desire for me to purchase products that were initially not on my shopping list.
Impulsive Buying	IB2	(Hilmi & Pratika, 2021)	2. The Pay Later feature steers me towards buying products that were not initially part of my shopping list.
	IB3		3. Pay Later feature makes me inclined to buy products that were not contemplated in my thoughts and on my shopping list.

Analyzing the data presented above, it can be concluded that female participation in filling out the questionnaire reached 56.7%, indicating their dominance among the respondents in this study. Delving deeper into the generational aspect, the data reveals a noteworthy dominance of Generation Z among Paylater users, comprising 56.7%. This finding signifies a high interest in Paylater services within this age group, highlighting a crucial market segment for service providers to consider in their strategic planning. Shifting attention to the choice of Paylater service providers, Shopee (Spaylater) emerges as a trailblazer, capturing 48.5% of respondent preferences. This preference aligns with the evolving trend of leveraging e-commerce platforms not only for product purchases but also for innovative financial solutions. The results underscore the significance of understanding demographic dynamics and consumer preferences for effective strategic planning in the competitive landscape of Paylater services. Interestingly, the student or university student group is also noted as Paylater users, accounting for a proportion of 32.9%. This provides an indication that this group has specific financial needs and preferences. Meanwhile, regarding the average monthly expenditures, 45.4% of respondents fall within the range of Rp501,000.00 to Rp1,500,000.00. This illustrates the variation in the scale of Paylater usage among respondents in this study. The findings from this research provide a comprehensive insight into the profile of Paylater users and their spending patterns. These insights can serve as a foundational reference to better understand financial behavior in the digital era.

Measurement Model

In assessing our measurement model, we employ the cutting-edge technique of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This method is intricately crafted to scrutinize composite and exploratory models that often grapple with a tenuous theoretical foundation. To ascertain the dimensions of our research constructs, our diligent researchers delve into a trio of crucial aspects: the reliability of internal consistency, the convergence of validity, and the distinctiveness of validity. Check out Table 3 for a snapshot of factor loading indicators surpassing the 0.50 threshold and boasting significance levels below 0.05—underscoring the pivotal role these indicators play in affirming the robustness of our measurement model. Additionally, Table 4 presents the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct, with assessment results surpassing 0.50. The AVE values in Table 4 demonstrate the strength of convergent validity for the constructs, aligning with the established criteria (Hair et al., 2019). Considering this rigorous analysis, it can be affirmed that the reliability and validity of the measurement model lay a solid foundation for the analysis and interpretation of findings in subsequent research.

Table 3. Factor loadings and descriptive properties of the measures

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
BNPL1 <- BNPL	0.771	0.741	0.098	7.829	0
BNPL2 <- BNPL	0.794	0.763	0.112	7.117	0
BNPL3 <- BNPL	0.83	0.82	0.052	16.006	0
HV1 <- Hedonic Value	0.907	0.898	0.04	22.647	0
HV2 <- Hedonic Value	0.923	0.914	0.039	23.472	0
HV3 <- Hedonic Value	0.878	0.864	0.055	16.076	0
IB1 <- Impulsive Buying	0.87	0.858	0.06	14.437	0
IB2 <- Impulsive Buying	0.854	0.835	0.077	11.104	0
IB3 <- Impulsive Buying	0.88	0.865	0.061	14.503	0
MF1 <- Utilizing Facilities	0.842	0.842	0.035	24.311	0
MF2 <- Utilizing Facilities	0.787	0.756	0.118	6.671	0
MF3 <- Utilizing Facilities	0.866	0.855	0.05	17.409	0

Table 4. Reliability and convergent validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
BNPL	0.715	0.715	0.841	0.638
Hedonic Value	0.886	0.886	0.93	0.815
Impulsive Buying	0.836	0.837	0.902	0.754
Utilizing Facilities	0.777	0.782	0.871	0.693

Table 5. Discriminant validity

	BNPL	HEDONIC VALUE	IMPULSIVE BUYING	UTILIZING FACILITIES
BNPL	0.798			
HEDONIC VALUE	0.79	0.903		
IMPULSIVE BUYING	0.796	0.881	0.868	
UTILIZING FACILITIES	0.823	0.83	0.82	0.832

Examining the report in Table 4, construct reliability is confirmed through three measures: Cronbach's alpha, Rho, and composite reliability (>0.70), in accordance with expert recommendations (Sarstedt et al., 2017). On another note, the Squared AVE guarantees that each construct surpasses other inter-correlation coefficients, solidifying the distinctiveness of each element in our analysis. (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Discriminant validity is assessed at the level of discriminant validity using the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) comparison method. This approach involves utilizing a multitrait-multimethod matrix as the measurement foundation. To ensure discriminant validity between two reflective constructs, the HTMT values should be less than 0.9 (Henseler et al., 2015). Observing the HTMT values presented in the table above, it can be concluded that all HTMT values are below 0.9. With these results, it can be stated that all constructs have demonstrated excellent levels of discriminant validity.

Structural Model

PLS-SEM can be utilized to analyze and test relationships between latent variables in a structural model. Particularly in social and business research, PLS-SEM has proven to be beneficial in understanding complex or intricate relationships among variables that are often not easily measured (Hair et al., 2019). After establishing reliability and validity in a measurement model, another suggested step is hypothesis testing through the application of bootstrap techniques, involving 5000 bootstrap resamples with bias correction. In evaluating the results, several key metrics can be employed, including beta values, t-values, p-values, explained variance (R-squared), and effect size coefficients (f-squared). It's noteworthy to pay attention to the interpretation of effect size, where values exceeding 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 can be classified as weak, moderate, and strong effects, respectively.

Table 6. Results of hypotheses testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Supported
BNPL -> Utilizing Facilities	0.823	0.802	0.077	10.66	0	Yes
BNPL -> Hedonic Value	0.79	0.789	0.059	13.302	0	Yes
Hedonic Value -> Impulsive Buying	0.644	0.613	0.155	4.159	0	Yes
Utilizing Facilities -> Impulsive Buying	0.286	0.312	0.141	2.027	0.043	Yes

The results of data analysis using the SEM PLS method indicate significant support for all the proposed research hypotheses. Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4, each linking specific variables in the model, consistently received strong support from the data. For each hypothesis, the p-values are as follows: H1, H2, and H3 have values of 0, and on the other hand H4 have values of 0.043 indicating that these hypotheses have a very low probability of occurring by chance alone. In statistical terms, p-values of 0 suggest strong evidence against the null hypothesis, supporting the alternative hypothesis. This finding suggests that the model processed using SEM PLS effectively reflects and supports the relationships among variables in the context of this research.

CONCLUSION

Research Conclusion

This study provides an overview of the conclusion that there is a positive relationship between utilizing Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) and leveraging payment facilities, aligning with previous research on harnessing technological advancements to enhance public services (Prabowo, 2021). Facilitating conditions, such as the availability of comprehensive guidance that assists users in navigating the technology, play a crucial role in motivating the community to embrace such advancements. The findings resonate with prior research indicating that facilitating conditions influence the user's interest in adopting pay later services (Adirineksa, 2021; Mukminin et al., 2019).

The results of the second hypothesis have confirmed that BNPL (Buy Now, Pay Later) has a positive impact on hedonistic lifestyle. This is grounded in the excessive consumptive behavior that has become ingrained in Indonesian society, particularly dominated by high levels of consumerism (Prastiwi & Fitria, 2021). This is further supported by the hedonic motivation arising from the use of technology (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The perceived pleasure derived from utilizing Pay Later motivates continuous usage among the community (Adirineksa, 2021).

The sway of digital payments on societal spending habits is undeniably positive, as the increasing use of digital payment methods correlates with a rise in consumptive behaviors (Naufalia, 2022). The simultaneous use of E-money and the ease of payment systems significantly impact consumptive behavior (Islami et al., 2023). Building upon these prior findings, this aligns with the hypothesis validation in this study, indicating that leveraging such facilities positively influences consumptive purchases.

The results of the final hypothesis validation reveal that a hedonistic lifestyle positively influences consumptive purchases, consistent with previous research establishing a connection between hedonistic lifestyle and consumptive behavior in adolescents. There is a positive correlation between a hedonistic lifestyle and consumptive behavior, signifying that as hedonistic lifestyle increases, so does consumptive behavior. Therefore, a higher hedonistic lifestyle is associated with a more consumptive behavior (Angraini & Santhoso, 2019; Thamrin & Saleh, 2021).

Theoretical and Managerial Implications

This study provides profound insights into financial behavior in the digital era, particularly concerning the use of pay-later services. The utilization of internet-facilitated payment systems, coupled with smartphone convenience for user mobility during transactions, signifies a transformative shift in financial practices (Suryadi et al., 2022). Transactions facilitated through collaborative applications with banks ensure transaction security.

The high adoption of pay-later services among predominantly millennial and Generation Z demographics contributes to understanding consumer dynamics based on generational and socio-economic status. The ease of technology in pay-later features supports impulsive buying tendencies, thereby driving consumptive behavior (Kadua et al., 2023). This research offers insights into Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) financing, a field increasingly sought after by marketers and business stakeholders. This information can be leveraged to develop more effective marketing strategies, especially in reaching diverse segments of the population. Additionally, it contributes to addressing the academic knowledge gap regarding BNPL. There is speculation suggesting that the materialistic aspect can influence the utilization of BNPL, potentially leading to impulsive buying behavior. (Raj et al., 2023).

Limitations and future direction

While this study is descriptive and correlational, offering rich insights into pay-later user profiles and measurement model validity, its limitations include potential gender bias affecting result generalization and inherent constraints in the research method that may restrict in-depth causal interpretation of latent variable relationships (Putri & Andarini, 2022).

Moreover, the research method employed in this study introduces limitations in terms of the depth of causal interpretation regarding latent variable relationships. The correlational nature of the study restricts the ability to make definitive causal claims, necessitating caution in drawing concrete conclusions about cause-and-effect dynamics among the observed variables.

To address these limitations and pave the way for future research endeavors, it is recommended to integrate qualitative approaches. Qualitative methods, such as focused interviews or group discussions, can provide a more in-depth understanding of the behaviors and preferences of users who opt for deferred payments. This qualitative dimension could uncover insights that quantitative methods alone may not fully capture.

For future research, it is recommended to integrate qualitative approaches for a deeper understanding of pay-later user behavior and preferences. Expanding the scope of variables and dimensions to detail additional factors influencing pay-later usage is advisable. Additionally, considering the potential for self-reporting bias from questionnaire users, exploring the potential integration of Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) services, given the sensitive financial information involved, future studies could emphasize security, privacy, and trust aspects surrounding BNPL usage (Alalwan et al., 2023).

REFERENCES

1. Adirinekso, G. P. (2021). Minat dan Penggunaan Fintech PayLater Pekerja Urban Pelanggan Traveloka dan GoJek Sebelum dan Selama Pandemi Covid 19 di DKI Jakarta. *Journal of Management and Business Review*, 18(2), 327–342. <https://doi.org/10.34149/jmbr.v18i2.283>
2. Alalwan, A. A., Baabdullah, A. M., Al-Debei, M. M., Raman, R., Alhitmi, H. K., Abu- ElSamen, A. A., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2023). Fintech and contactless payment: Help or hindrance? The role of invasion of privacy and information disclosure. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-08-2022-0339>
3. Anggraini, R. T., & Santhoso, F. H. (2019). Hubungan antara Gaya Hidup Hedonis dengan Perilaku Konsumtif pada Remaja. *Gadjah Mada Journal of Psychology (GamaJoP)*, 3(3), 131. <https://doi.org/10.22146/gamajop.44104>
4. Aristanti, N. D. (2020). Pay Later, Kartu Kredit Zaman Now yang Ternyata Bisa Bikin Kalap Belanja! <https://koinworks.com/blog/apa-itu-pay-later/>
5. Azzahra, W. (2022). Analisis Use Behavior Terhadap Pengguna Shopee Paylater Menggunakan Modifikasi Model UTAUT 2.
6. Babin, B. J., & Attaway, J. S. (2000). Atmospheric Affect as a Tool for Creating Value and Gaining Share of Customer. *Journal of Business Research*, 49(2), 91–99. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(99\)00011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(99)00011-9)
7. Eviana, V., & Saputra, A. J. (2022). Analisis Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Minat Penggunaan Sistem Pembayaran Pay Later. *Tambusai*, 6(1), 1968–1977.
8. Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224378101800104>
9. Ginantra, Janner, N. L., Purba, Tojiri, R. A., M. Y., Duwila, A. A, Siregar, & Siswanti. (2020). *Teknologi Finansial: Sistem Finansial Berbasis Teknologi di Era Digital*. Yayasan Kita Menulis.
10. Gupta, Anil, Nikita, D. G., & Babu, G. (2017). What Determines Tourist Adoption of Smartphone Apps? An Analysis Based On The UTAUT2 Framework.
11. Guttman-Kenney, B., Firth, C., & Gathergood, J. (2023). Buy now, pay later (BNPL) ...on your credit card. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 37, 100788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbef.2023.100788>
12. Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
13. Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
14. Hilmi, L. D., & Pratika, Y. (2021). Paylater Feature: Impulsive Buying Driver FOR E-COMMERCE IN INDONESIA. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 5(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebar.v5i2.2337>
15. Hirschman, E. C., & Holbrook, M. B. (1982). Hedonic Consumption: Emerging Concepts, Methods and Propositions. *Journal of Marketing*, 46(3), 92–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224298204600314>
16. Islami, F., Rafidah, & Lubis, P. A. (2023). Pengaruh Penggunaan E-Money dan Sistem Pembayaran Shopee Paylater Terhadap Perilaku Konsumtif Mahasiswa FEBI UIN Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin Jambi dalam Perspektif Syari'ah. *INFOTECH journal*, 9(2), 339–344. <https://doi.org/10.31949/infotech.v9i2.6072>

17. Iyer, G. R., Blut, M., Xiao, S. H., & Grewal, D. (2020). Impulse buying: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48(3), 384–404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-019-00670-w>
18. Joines, J. L., Scherer, C. W., & Scheufele, D. A. (2003). Exploring motivations for consumer Web use and their implications for e-commerce.
19. Kadua, N. C. P., Safitri, R. D., & Afyah, R. N. (2023). Kajian Strategis Consumptive Behavior Dalam Penerapan Buy Now Pay Later di Shopee dengan Islamic Financial Literacy Sebagai Moderasi.
20. Kollat, D. T., & Willett, R. P. (1967). Customer Impulse Purchasing Behavior. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 4(1), 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224376700400102>
21. Lantini, S. B. S., Maulana, R. A., Putri, M. A., & Kartini, E. (2023). Peran Otoritas Jasa Keuangan dalam Pengawasan Paylater pada Aplikasi Shopee. *Universitas Tidar*, 2, 2.
22. Mukminin, A., Rachman, R., & Wahyudi, H. (2019). Penerapan Model UTAUT untuk Perilaku Pengguna “Paylater” di dalam Traveloka.
23. Naufalia, V. (2022). Pengaruh Digital Payment dan E-Service Quality Terhadap Perilaku Konsumtif pada Pengguna Shopee Wilayah DKI Jakarta.
24. Prabowo, M. T. (2021). Universitas Islam Sultan Agung Fakultas Ekonomi Program Studi AKuntansi Semarang 202.
25. Prastiwi, I. E., & Fitria, T. N. (2021). Konsep Paylater Online Shopping dalam Pandangan Ekonomi Islam. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Islam*, 7(1), 425. <https://doi.org/10.29040/jiei.v7i1.1458>
26. Pratika, Y., Salahudin, S., & Ambarwati, T. (2021). Analysis of Pay Later Payment System on Online Shopping in Indonesia. *Journal of Economics, Business, & Accountancy Ventura*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.14414/jebav.v23i3.2343>
27. Putri, N. M. E., & Andarini, S. (2022). Pengaruh Self Control dan Financial Attitude terhadap Financial Management Behavior pengguna Layanan Buy Now Pay Later. *Jurnal Ekonomi Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 21(1), 60–74. <https://doi.org/10.19184/jeam.v21i1.30594>
28. Raj, V. A., Jasrotia, S. S., & Rai, S. S. (2023). Intensifying materialism through buy-now pay- later (BNPL): Examining the dark sides. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-08-2022-0343>
29. Rook, D. W. (1987). The Buying Impulse. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 14(2), 189–199. <https://doi.org/10.1086/209105>
30. Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2017). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. In C. Homburg, M. Klarmann, & A. Vomberg (Eds.), *Handbook of Market Research* (pp. 1–40). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05542-8_15-1
31. Suryadi, N., Linda, R., Yusnelly, A., Kusdiana, Y., & Rahma, S. (2022). Literasi Digital: Mewujudkan Penggunaan Uang Elektronik dalam bertransaksi dikalangan kaum Milenial di Kota Pekanbaru. *Azam Insan Cendikia*, 1(1), Article 1.
32. Thamrin, H., & Saleh, A. A. (2021). Hubungan Antara Gaya Hidup Hedonis dengan Perilaku Konsumtif pada Mahasiswa. 11.
33. Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis. (2003). User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
34. Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000a). A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>
35. Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000b). A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>
36. Widawati, L. (2011). Analisis Perilaku “Impulse Buying” dan “Locus of Control” pada Konsumen di Carrefour Bandung. *MIMBAR : Jurnal Sosial dan Pembangunan*, 27(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.29313/mimbar.v27i2.320>
37. Zhong, J. Y., & Mitchell, V.-W. (2010). A mechanism model of the effect of hedonic product consumption on well-being. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 20(2), 152–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2010.01.001>

Cite this Article: Rochma, Y.D., Suryandari, R.T. (2025). Has Buy Now Pay Later become a symbol of hedonistic lifestyle among young people?. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(5), pp. 2569-2578. DOI: https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i5-68